

AN ANALYSIS OF CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR AND PREFERENCES TOWARDS WASHING MACHINE IN TIRUCHIRAPPALLI DISTRICT

Dr. R. Jayasri, M.Com, M.Phil, B.Ed, M.B.A, Ph.D.

Associate Professor, PG & Research Department of Management Studies,

Thanthi Hans Rovers College, Perambalur.

ABSTRACT

There are some major classes of consumer preference determinants and expectations, namely, price of the product, brand loyalty, after sales service, durability, appearance, promotional offers, technology, and dealer relationship. The demographic factors age, gender, educational qualification, marital status, occupation, residential area, size of family and monthly income etc., with the consumer about washing machine toughs in the towns of Tiruchirappalli district are different. So the dealers/vendors should consider the demographic factors of consumers while marketing their products. There are certain factors which influence purchase decision which will satisfy the consumers of Washing machine. The manufacturers of washing machine should concentrate on these features as there may be the choice of a few more prospective buyers. With growing technological improvements in the world, the manufacturers should introduce new technological goods in production of washing machine. So, the manufacturers and dealers should study the preference of consumers in order to cater to their needs and then only they can be successful. The present paper focuses on to analyses the socio demographic profile of the respondents, to find out consumer preference of washing machine in Tiruchirappalli district and to give suitable suggestions to improve consumer preference of washing machine

INTRODUCTION

At present the market situation in India is highly competitive across all the product segments. With the continuous evolution in the demographics and psychographics of the targeted consumers, the situation is becoming more and more complex. The ever changing customer preferences, rising consumerism, new entrants in the market, and continuously evolving technological innovations resulting in product differentiation in the short run which further resulting in shorter life cycles for durables particularly and also for other lifestyle products are adding new dimensions to already complex situation.

The preferences of the consumers are a positive motivation, expressed by the affective compatibility towards a product, service or trading form. We're not dealing with an internal bodily function, but a quality of objects that aims to fulfill our needs, quality acquired within the

connection between man and the merchandise able to fulfill these needs. Preferences can be triggered by: the features related to the material substance of the goods (shape, size, print, taste, colour, consistency, package, etc.); elements referring to label, name, use instructions that accompany the product; the statute granted to the person owning and using that particular product.

Studying the consumer's preference is not an easy task at all, and even less simple is observing only one aspect of this preference, like in the present case, the consumers' preference for a certain product, label or organisation. Along the research consumers may express their needs and desires and still may act in a totally opposite way; at times, it's possible that they aren't even aware of the true motivations behind their buying behavior, or they could react to factors determining last minute changes to their buying decision. The consumer decisions are relatively easy to notice and quantify, the psycho-physiological processes behind them are very difficult to take into account. Research related to consumer preference looks upon its different dimensions and their relationship. The final aim of his investigations is to foresee and channel the future reactions of the demand agents, for a precise correlation between demand and supply. In this respect, all dimensions that lead to the manifestation of a certain preference must be studied and understood. Each of the dimensions of the consumers' preference which is to be focused on within a marketing research imprints on it with certain specificity, a special way of approach. Therefore, the special features of the consumers' preferences mark certain specific features in this sense, which must be taken into consideration in view of observing the essence of this dimension of the consumers' preference.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The following are the review of literature relating to the present study.

Sudharsana Reddy and Rajalashmi (2007) revealed that the electronic industry was in its nascent stage of development till 1970. In the Age of Globalization, it is one of the fastest growing industries in India. They analysed the buyer behaviour in microwave ovens and found that all buyers have by nature, different tastes, likes and dislikes and adopt different behaviour pattern while making buying decisions.

Anand Thakur and Hundal (2008) suggested that both rural and urban consumers differed in their perception about washing machine as an item of necessity. The urban consumers were highly influenced by the washing machine compared to rural and preferred to put them in 'necessity' category.

Dr.S.Sarvana (2010) In his article in Indian Journal of marketing entitled "A study on consumer behavior of woman with special reference to durable goods in Coimbatore City, Tamil Nadu", found that education plays a key role in shopping behavior and higher income group respondents shop as and when they like; In majority women plays a major role in purchase

decision and they prefer to prepare an item list before purchasing. Family influences the consumer's behavior to a greater extent while purchasing. Majority of the respondents prefer to purchase products from departmental store rather than any other shop. Most of the people recommend the product purchased by them to others. People give preference to product quality. Most of them satisfied with the factors such as price, quality, and availability of service and design of durable goods. In the present study we are internal to know wither people in Allahabad City as satisfied with the price, quality, availability, service and design of electronic goods.

Dr.S.Aravinth (2012) the preference of customers is nothing but the required a product or commodity according to their expected features and attributes. In this regard the researcher is dealt with the housewife and taken them as respondents in the name of customer on their choices of purchasing electronic goods. In this fast moving world, the city life has much more advanced in many schedules. Without the adoption of electronic good one family could not be a competed one in the society. The family is always lead by the women, who shares the half of the burden of the leader for a family. In such a situation she preference more advanced and supporting commodities which fulfils her day to day works. The researcher has designed a framework or a task which is actually leads to find the significant relationship between the wife acceptance factor and the electronic goods. This will also gives an opportunity to the retailer who actually deals with the electronic consumer goods, to know the exact behaviour of the family administrator on purchasing electronic commodities.

R.Karthika, Dr. N.VijaiAnand(2017) "A study on consumer buying behavior towards selected white goods with special reference to Tiruchirapalli District" found that demand for consumer white goods is highly flexible due to the change in the business condition. Consumer insists for the reveal of all technical details relating to the product. They decide to purchase the product after through enquiry of the product with the dealers of a particular brand.

S.R.Dass andD.P.Misra (2018) "An empirical study on factors influencing the buying behavior of consumer towards washing machine, Balasore town, Odisha", observed that consumers are aware of the availability of various brand and prefer to purchase the product from known retailers. They are satisfied with the performance of the brand they selected. Demographic factor does not affect the choice of particular brand. But various factors such as price quality, model and others have a great influence on purchase choice.

Kiruthiga Elangovan (2019) suggested that Consumer durables industry is facing a steady growth rate in the Indian economy due to the high disposable income and easy financing options. Nowadays consumer durables are considered as an essential rather than a luxury. This paper conducts the consumer behavior through Nicosia model of consumer behavior where the

consumer's attitude their search and evaluation of products their purchase decision and the post purchase behavior were taken for study.

Meerabai (2020) examined the consumer behaviour with special focus on women consumer and their need for select products and services. The main focus is on their general buying behaviour and to find out whether there is an associate between certain facture with few variables of women's buying behaviour. The study revealed that the women respondents give importance to price of the product rather them the quality of the product.

The review of past studies helps the researcher to frame the objectives of the present study.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Consumer is the King of market environment and all the marketing activities of all the business and industrial enterprises of today go around the habits, tastes, preferences, perception and attitudes of consumers. All efforts are being made to provide maximum satisfaction to maximum consumers. Especially consumer in the durable white goods industry is experiencing increased globalization, competition, higher customer turnover, growing customer acquisition costs and rising customer expectations, meaning that durable industry performance and competitiveness is significantly dependent on their ability to satisfy the customer effectively and efficiently. In the consumer durable industry, the basic products are very similar and when comparing the same quality level, the customer focuses are on soft factors like personal treatment, personalization, one-to-one marketing and attention of the customers.

In order to be competing a high competitive market, durable products has to meet every single customer's wants and expectations and to do this, it is important to study the aspects of business performances that convince customers to become repeat purchasers and to exhibit consumer preference towards brand loyalty.

Further, a buyer purchases a product because of certain physical, social and economical forces creating a desire or a want for the product. A decision to buy a product of daily use may be taken in few seconds while the decision to buy a durable product is taken after critical study of many factors. Consumers frequently change their shopping behaviour. This is a major issue for company to predict their future and profitability. But main point is that why consumer change their choices frequently, and why they purchase some product and why not other one. That is why researcher felt this study is important to study in order to provide suitable suggestion to improve sales and promotions.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study has the following objectives, which are examined in the case of washing machine

- To analyses the socio demographic profile of the respondents
- To find out consumer preference of washing machine in Tiruchirappalli district
- To give suitable suggestions to improve consumer preference of washing machine

UNIVERSE OF THE STUDY

Collection, population, or set of entities, items, or quantities (grouped together on the basis of common or defining characteristics or features) from which a representative sample is drawn for comparison or measurement. The present study universe is undefined; therefore to make the research manageable the universe of the proposed study is on consumers within the Tiruchirappalli District.

List of Top 10 Washing Machine Brands

- LG
- Videocon
- Samsung
- Whirlpool
- Onida
- Godrej
- IFB
- Haier
- Panasonic
- Weston

METHODOLOGY

Methodology is the systematic, theoretical analysis of the methods applied to a field of study. It comprises the theoretical analysis of the body of methods and principles associated with a branch of knowledge. Typically, it encompasses concepts such as paradigm, theoretical model, phases and quantitative or qualitative techniques. The present study is an exploratory in nature. A different method of data collection was applied to complete the survey work.

Sampling and Sample Size

Sampling is a process used in statistical analysis in which a predetermined number of observations will be taken from a larger population. The methodology used to sample from a larger population will depend on the type of analysis being performed. The present study is selected the sample by using of disproportionate stratified random sampling technique. The

Tiruchirappalli district has 11 Taluks. The following Table 1 shows the name of the Taluks and the number of respondents selected for the present study.

Table - 1
Taluks in Tiruchirappalli District.

S. No	Name of the Taluk	No. of Respondents
1	Tiruchirappalli –East	75
2	Tiruchirappalli -West	75
3	Tiruverambur	75
4	Srirangam	75
5	Manapparai	75
6	Marungapuri	75
7	Lalgudi	75
8	Mannachanallur	75
9	Musiri	75
10	Thottiam	75
11	Thuraiyur	75
	Total	825

Each Taluk consists of 75 targeted respondents based on simple random sampling. The respondents from various showrooms, retail store and malls which are located around these 11 taluks and also researcher have personally met with friends and family friends to study the in-depth views of buying behaviour and preference towards washing machine users. In practice, the sample size used in a study is determined based on data collection, and the need to have sufficient statistical power. The present study is confined the sample size is 825. It is found that there are 11 Taluks in Tiruchirappalli District and 75 respondents have been selected for each taluk with a total of 825 from Tiruchirappalli District.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Data analysis is considered to be an important step and heart in research work. After collection of data with the help of relevant tools and techniques, the next logical step, is to analyze and interpret data with a view to arriving at empirical solution to the problem.

The data analysis for the present research was done quantitatively with the help of both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistical techniques like percentage analysis, mean, Standard Deviation and for the inferential statistics. For the analysis of respondents Chi-square, Student 't' test, One way ANOVA 'f' test were applied. For the analysis of the collected data, both descriptive and differential analysis has been done by the researcher.

Table – 2

Cross tabulation between Taluks wise and age group wise classification

Name of Taluks	Age									
	Below 30yrs		31 to 40yrs		41 to 50yrs		51yrs and above		Total	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Tiruchirappalli -East	17	22.7%	25	33.3%	16	21.3%	17	22.7%	75	100.0%
Tiruchirappalli -West	26	34.7%	27	36.0%	11	14.7%	11	14.7%	75	100.0%
Tiruverumbur	17	22.7%	32	42.7%	11	14.7%	15	20.0%	75	100.0%
Srirangam	22	29.3%	29	38.7%	10	13.3%	14	18.7%	75	100.0%
Manapparai	15	20.0%	28	37.3%	18	24.0%	14	18.7%	75	100.0%
Marungapuri	20	26.7%	21	28.0%	14	18.7%	20	26.7%	75	100.0%
Lalgudi	26	34.7%	22	29.3%	13	17.3%	14	18.7%	75	100.0%
Manachanallur	21	28.0%	21	28.0%	14	18.7%	19	25.3%	75	100.0%
Musiri	16	21.3%	21	28.0%	20	26.7%	18	24.0%	75	100.0%
Thottium	23	30.7%	21	28.0%	15	20.0%	16	21.3%	75	100.0%
Thuraiyur	11	14.7%	22	29.3%	20	26.7%	22	29.3%	75	100.0%
Total	214	25.9%	269	32.6%	162	19.6%	180	21.8%	825	100.0%

Source: Primary data (Row wise percentage)

The above table reveals that one third (33.3 per cent) of the respondents were 31 to 40 years of age people and 22.7 per cent of the respondents were below 30 years and above 51years in Tiruchirappalli-East Taluk. More than one third (36per cent) of the respondents were 31 to 40years and 34.7 per cent of the respondent were below 30 years in Tiruchirappalli-West Taluk. More than

one third (42.7 per cent) of the respondent were 31 to 40 years and 22.7 per cent of the respondents were below 30 years in Thiruverumbur Taluk. More than one third (38.7 per cent) of the respondent were 31 to 40 years and 29.3 per cent of the respondents were below 30years in Srirangam Taluk. More than one third (37.3 per cent) of the respondent were 31 to 40years and 24per cent of the respondents were 41 to 50years in Manapparai Taluk. Nearly one third (28 per cent) of the respondents were 41 to 50years and 26.7 per cent of the respondents were below 30 years and above 51years in Marungapuri Taluk. One third (34.7per cent) of the respondents were below 30years and 29.3 per cent of the respondents were 31 to 40 years in Lalgudi Taluk. Nearly one third (28per cent) of the respondents were below 30years and 31 to 40years and 25.3per cent of the respondents were in above 51 years in Mannachanallur Taluk. Nearly one third (28per cent) of the respondents were below 31 to 40years and 26.7 per cent of the respondents were in 41 to 50 years in Musiri Taluk. One third (30.7 per cent) of the respondents were below 30 years and 28 per cent of the respondents were in 31 to 40 years in Thottiam Taluk. Nearly one third (29.3 per cent) of the respondents were 31 to 40years and above 51years and 26.7 per cent of the respondents were in 41 to 50 years in Thuraiyur Taluk. In almost all the Taluks, the respondent’s age ranges from 30 to 50 years.

Table – 3

Cross tabulation between Taluks wise and media wise influence to buy the washing machine based on Taluks.

Name of Taluks	Influence of media to buy the product													
	Television		Radio		Newspaper		Magazines		Billboards		Internet		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Tiruchirappalli -East	28	37.3%	4	5.3%	15	20.0%	5	6.7%	8	10.7%	15	20.0%	75	100.0%
Tiruchirappalli -West	30	40.0%	4	5.3%	17	22.7%	6	8.0%	7	9.3%	11	14.7%	75	100.0%
Tiruverumbur	27	36.0%	7	9.3%	16	21.3%	5	6.7%	9	12.0%	11	14.7%	75	100.0%
Srirangam	27	36.0%	10	13.3%	18	24.0%	7	9.3%	2	2.7%	11	14.7%	75	100.0%
Manapparai	30	40.0%	10	13.3%	20	26.7%	1	1.3%	5	6.7%	9	12.0%	75	100.0%
Marungapuri	29	38.7%	11	14.7%	18	24.0%	1	1.3%	8	10.7%	8	10.7%	75	100.0%
Lalgudi	23	30.7%	7	9.3%	18	24.0%	11	14.7%	2	2.7%	14	18.7%	75	100.0%
Manachanallur	18	24.0%	8	10.7%	21	28.0%	7	9.3%	2	2.7%	19	25.3%	75	100.0%

Musiri	32	42.7%	8	10.7%	22	29.3%	7	9.3%	3	4.0%	3	4.0%	75	100.0%
Thottium	22	29.3%	6	8.0%	24	32.0%	8	10.7%	2	2.7%	13	17.3%	75	100.0%
Thuraiyur	24	32.0%	12	16.0%	14	18.7%	6	8.0%	4	5.3%	15	20.0%	75	100.0%
Total	290	35.2%	87	10.5%	203	24.6%	64	7.8%	52	6.3%	129	15.6%	825	100.0%

Source: Primary data (Row wise percentage)

The above table indicates that more than one third (37.3 per cent) of the respondents were influenced by television and 20 per cent of the respondents were to buy the product influenced from Newspaper and Internet in Tiruchirappalli-East Taluk. More than one third (40 per cent) of the respondents were influenced by Television and 22.7 per cent of the respondents were influenced by Newspaper in Tiruchirappalli-West Taluk. More than one third (36 per cent) of the respondents were to buy influenced from Television and 21.3 cent of the respondents were influenced by newspaper in Tiruverambur Taluk. More than one third (36per cent) of the respondents were influenced by television and 24 per cent of the respondents were influenced by newspaper in Srirangam Taluk. More than one third (40 per cent) of the respondents were influenced by Television and 26.7 per cent of the respondents were influenced by newspaper in Manapparai Taluk. More than one third (38.7 per cent) of the respondents were influenced by television and 24 per cent of the respondents were influenced by newspaper in Marungapuri Taluk. One third (30.7 per cent) of the respondents were influenced by television and 24 per cent of the respondents were influenced by newspaper in Lalgudi Taluk. More than one fourth (28 per cent) of the respondents were influenced by newspaper and 25.3per cent of the respondents were influenced by internet in Mannachanallur Taluk. More than one third (42.7per cent) of the respondent were influenced by television and 29.3per cent of the respondent were influenced by newspaper in Musiri Taluk. One third (32per cent) of the respondents were influenced by newspaper and 29.3per cent of the respondents were influenced by television in Thottiam Taluk. One third (32 per cent) of the respondents were influenced by television and 20 per cent of the respondents were influenced by internet in Thuraiyur Taluk.

Table – 4

Association between brand influence of washing machine and overall consumer preference

Research hypothesis (H₁): There is a significant association between brand influence of washing machine and overall consumer preference

Null hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant association between brand influence of washing machine and overall consumer preference

Overall brand influence of washing machine	Overall consumer preference						Statistical inference
	Low		High		Total		
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>N</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	
Low	228	57.1%	199	46.7%	427	51.8%	X ² =8.975 Df=1 .003<0.05 Significant
High	171	42.9%	227	53.3%	398	48.2%	
Total	399	100.0%	426	100.0%	825	100.0%	

Statistical test: Chi-square test was used the above hypothesis

The hypothesis was tested with the help of Chi-square test to find out whether there is a significant association between brand influence of washing machine and overall consumer preference. It is found that the calculated value which is less than table value ($P < 0.05$). So the research hypothesis is accepted and null hypothesis rejected.

From the above analysis, it is found that there is significant association between brand influence of washing machine and overall consumer preference.

FINDINGS

The following are the findings of the above study.

- From Table 1, it is found that there are 11 Taluks in Tiruchirappalli District and 75 respondents have been selected for each taluk with a total of 825 respondents who buy washing machine in Tiruchirappalli District.
- From Table 2, it is found that One third (32.6 per cent) of the respondents between the age group of 31 to 40yrs, 25.9 per cent of the respondents were below 30yrs, 21.8 per cent of the respondents were 51yrs and above and remaining 19.6 per cent of the respondents were 41 to 50yrs.
- From Table 3, it is found that One third (35.2 per cent) of the respondents were influenced by Television, 24.6 per cent of the respondents were influenced by newspaper, 15.6 per cent of the respondents were influenced by internet, 10.5 per cent of the respondents were influenced by radio, 7.8 per cent of the respondents were magazines, 6.3 per cent of the respondents were influenced by Billboards.
- From Table 4, it is found that there is a significant association between brand influences of washing machine and overall consumer preference.

SUGGESTIONS

The following are the suggestions.

- It is suggested that consumer preference which is characterized as more significant in its nature at market environment, has been subject to research often. With the regard the companies should take initiate and promote a regular monitoring and of consumers preference towards their products features and brand range.
- Purchase decision process which is one of the factors influenced in consumer buying preference on particular brand. Basically family members influence in the purchase decision process is to be considered more significant than the influence of any other factor, for the most important reason, the power of decision process in family that decides the level of consumption pattern, choice of products, brands, color and etc., related aspects of product. In order to reach the prospective buyer without any complications, is to recognize the person dominating the decision making process he / she is to be influenced in the desired action.
- The marketers of particular washing machine should insist all the technical information on the use of products with any technical fault and avoid frequent repairs, free servicing of machines to during the guarantee period insisted upon the consumers and
- It is also suggested by the researcher that awareness being the first element of purchase process, the manufactures need to focus on the customer awareness in a better way for achieving the results. Therefore, brand image is caused by the brand awareness and so brand awareness should be created to pull the customers towards purchase of a particular product.

CONCLUSION

Now days , the consumers in towns of Tiruchirappalli district are increasingly buying more and using different brands of washing machine. So, an understanding of the consumer preference enables the marketers to take marketing decision which are compatible with consumer needs.

There are some major classes of consumer preference determinants and expectations, namely, price of the product, brand loyalty, after sales service, durability, appearance, promotional offers, technology, and dealer relationship. The demographic factors age, gender, educational qualification, marital status, occupation, residential area, size of family and monthly income etc., with the consumer about washing machine toughs in the towns of Tiruchirappalli district are different. So the dealers/vendors should consider the demographic factors of consumers while marketing their products.

From the conversation made in the previous chapters, there are certain factors which are identified in the study as influencing purchase decision and satisfied the consumers. The manufacturers of washing machine should concentrate on these features as they may be the choice of a few more prospective buyers. With growing technological improvements in the world, the manufacturers should introduce new technological goods in production of washing machine. So, the manufacturers and dealers should study the preference of consumers and cater to their needs to be successful.

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